

Vedic Approach to a Short Internode

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Abstract

In this brief paper, the authors present the Vedic solution of the discretized equation representing the internode of a myelinated axon.

The Vedic method for solving inhomogeneous simultaneous equations is adopted in this paper. The method makes use of the formula “samkalana-vyavakalanabhyam” presented in [1]. The equation to be solved is,

$$C \frac{\partial V(x, t)}{\partial t} = \kappa \frac{\partial^2 V(x, t)}{\partial x^2} - GV(x, t). \quad (1)$$

We make use of the discretization prescription,

$$\frac{\partial V(x, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{V(i, n+1) - V(i, n)}{\Delta t}, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 V(x, t)}{\partial x^2} = \frac{1}{2(\Delta x)^2} [(V(i+1, n+1) - 2V(i, n+1) + V(i-1, n+1)) + \dots], \quad (3)$$

$$\dots + (V(i+1, n) - 2V(i, n) + V(i-1, n))] \quad (4)$$

and

$$V(x, t) = \frac{V(i, n+1) + V(i, n)}{2}. \quad (5)$$

Utilizing the discretization, we obtain,

$$\alpha V(i, n+1) + \beta V(i, n) - \gamma [V(i+1, n+1) + V(i-1, n+1) + V(i+1, n) + V(i-1, n)] = 0. \quad (6)$$

Suppose, i is 1 or 2. That is, we have a two segment axon. This yields the following simultaneous equations where the $i = 1$ case is displayed first, and then the $i = 2$ case:

$$\alpha V(1, n+1) + \beta V(1, n) - \gamma [V(2, n+1) + V(0, n+1) + V(2, n) + V(0, n)] = 0 \quad (7)$$

and

$$\alpha V(2, n+1) + \beta V(2, n) - \gamma [V(3, n+1) + V(1, n+1) + V(3, n) + V(1, n)] = 0 \quad (8)$$

Next, we denote, $V(0, n)$ as x , $V(0, n+1)$ as y , $V(1, n)$ as z , $V(1, n+1)$ as a , $V(2, n)$ as b and $V(2, n+1)$ as c , $V(3, n)$ as d and $V(3, n+1)$ as e for this truncated problem. We will assume that $V(\cdot, n)$ is the known case and we will find the solution for the $n+1$ case. The base case, $V(\cdot, 1)$ is the initial condition, which is also assumed to be given. Thus induction will complete the entire temporal trajectory. The boundary conditions determine $V(0, \cdot)$ and $V(3, \cdot)$. In this case, those are x, y, d and e . The two simultaneous equations become,

$$\alpha a - \gamma c = -\beta z + \gamma y + \gamma b + \gamma x \quad (9)$$

and

$$-\gamma a + \alpha c = -\beta b + \gamma d + \gamma e + \gamma z. \quad (10)$$

As per the sutra, we find their sum and difference to ease out the solution. Thus,

$$(\alpha - \gamma)a + (\alpha - \gamma)c = -\beta(z + b) + \gamma(y + b + x + d + e + z) \quad (11)$$

and

$$(\alpha + \gamma)a - (\alpha + \gamma)c = \beta(b - z) + \gamma(y + b + x - d - e - z). \quad (12)$$

Upon simplification we get,

$$(\alpha - \gamma)(a + c) = RHS_1 \quad (13)$$

and

$$(\alpha + \gamma)(a - c) = RHS_2 \quad (14)$$

These are easily used to get,

$$a = \frac{RHS_1}{2(\alpha - \gamma)} + \frac{RHS_2}{2(\alpha + \gamma)} \quad (15)$$

and hence,

$$c = \frac{RHS_1}{2(\alpha - \gamma)} - \frac{RHS_2}{(\alpha + \gamma)}. \quad (16)$$

With a and c , we obtain $V(1, 2)$ and $V(2, 2)$. Using these we would obtain $V(1, 3)$ and $V(2, 3)$ and so on, the entire temporal trajectory for the two segments is determined.

References

- [1] Swami Bharati Krishna Tirtha, Vasudeva Sharana Agrawala, et al. *Vedic mathematics*, volume 10. Motilal Banarsidass Publ., 1992.